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T-CAP: FRAMEWORK TO DESIGN STUDENT-CENTRIC COURSES USING EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGY TOOLS

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ABSTRACT

The use of educational technology tools has been steadily increasing in higher education in the last two decades. However, we have witnessed a widespread adoption of educational technology tools during lockdowns imposed by governments as a result of the COVID19 pandemic. Faculty were forced to identify technology tools that support online mode of instruction and continue their teaching virtually. The lack of training and time required to successfully adopt educational technology tools has impacted the quality of teaching and learning. Due to a lack of necessary knowledge and skills, faculty ended up focussing on identifying and utilizing technology tools that were convenient to them without trying to understand how they need to be contextualized based on the course outcomes and the learning requirements of the students. Students therefore would struggle to transition from in-person to online mode of teaching as the course were not anymore student-centric in nature. In this paper, we propose a framework T-CAP (Technology-Content Assessment Pedagogy) that could be employed by faculty to design and integrate educational technology tools in a student-centric way. T-CAP emphasizes the need for faculty to constructively align technology tools to all the three elements of a course – content, assessment, and pedagogy – and highlights how technology-content, technology-assessment, and technology-pedagogy should be aligned so

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that courses designed using technology tools are student-centric. The T-CAP models is being proposed as an extension to the widely known TPACK framework which emphasizes the need for alignment of technology tools with the content and pedagogy of the course. T-CAP encourages instructors to also think about the relation between technology and assessment and would be a valuable resource to faculty who intend to make blended/online learning their primary mode of teaching in a post- pandemic world.

1 INTRODUCTION

Higher education in the last two decades has witnessed a steady but gradual rate in the adoption of technology tools to support instructional practices. In spite of the numerous research available that indicates the benefits of using technology tools for classroom instruction for both students and the instructors, traditional lecturing continued to be the predominant mode of instruction for STEM courses [1]. The slow rate of adoption has often been attributed to the lack of knowledge and skills among the instructors to identify, learn, and make use of technology tools that could support and enhance their instructional practices. Prior faculty development efforts taken up to train the instructors have been reported to focus more on the technology usage with limited efforts spent to contextualize the technology tools based on the requirements of the course, students, and instructors [2]. The improper integration of technology tools has been reported to have a negative impact on the students' learning due to increase in cognitive load [3]. Mishra attempted to address these concerns as he introduced the Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) framework which emphasized the thoughtful alignment of the technological knowledge with the pedagogical content knowledge of the course [4].

The TPACK framework has been widely adopted in the last decade by various faculty developers and technology experts to train instructors in K-12 and higher education to thoughtfully integrate technology tools by understanding the integration between technology and content and technology and pedagogy. However, the TPACK framework has failed to elaborate on the alignment between the third important element of a course i.e. assessment. It overlooked the need to also understand how the technology tools being adopted can support the design, implementation, and evaluation of assessments in a course. In this paper, we attempt to fill this gap through the introduction of T-CAP (Technology-Content Assessment and Pedagogy) framework that will guide course instructors to utilize educational technology tools and design technology-enhanced courses. T-CAP emphasizes the need to constructively align the technology tools with content, assessment, and pedagogy of the course. The COVID19 pandemic has forced all instructors to rethink about education through the lens of technology and we believe the T-CAP framework will be an essential guide to all instructors in the post pandemic world to redesign their courses using technology tools through student-centric approach.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Adoption of Educational Technology in Higher Education

There is a large body of literature available that highlights the benefits of utilizing technology tools to support instructional practices [5]. The usage of technology was observed to specifically support students in developing deeper learning skills such as

critical thinking and problems-solving [6], collaboration in teams, and self-regulated learning [7]. However, the slow adoption of technology in courses has been attributed to multiple reasons such as lack of knowledge of technology, skills on how to effectively integrate technology tools, and resistance to change their teaching practices [8]. It was observed that the process of adoption of technology tools was a time consuming process [9], as most faculty were required to rethink their course design process and change their conceptions of the affordances of technology tools in education. The common practice, to identify and replicate technology tools in different courses, has shown to be largely ineffective as it's important to adapt technology to the learning requirements of the course, need of the students, and responsibilities of the instructor. With the growing calls to adopt technology-enhanced learning, there is a need to train instructors and equip them with the essential knowledge and skills to be able to design learning environments that are situated to their context.

2.2 Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK)

Mishra and Koehler introduced TPACK as a conceptual framework and defined it as a body of knowledge that would enable instructors to effectively integrate technology tools based on their context of operation [4]. They believed an instructor who possesses TPACK should build 1. Technological Content Knowledge (TCK) – which indicates the relationship with technology and content, as the use of technology would allow newer and varied flexibility to represent the course content; and 2. Technological Pedagogical Knowledge (TPK) – understand how the affordances of technology could support and hinder the implementation of innovation pedagogical practices. The development of TCK and TPK along with pedagogical content knowledge would lead to the construction of TPACK which would include knowledge of what makes concepts in course easy or difficult to learn, knowledge of challenges encountered by students in attaining the learning outcomes of the course, knowledge of the challenges they encountered as part of their responsibilities as an instructor, and knowledge how technology can help overcome all of these challenges. Although the TPACK framework has been widely appreciated and adopted especially to train instructors, the framework overlooks the important connection between technology and assessment. This study addresses this gap by proposing a new framework T-CAP which promotes the essential alignment of technology to all three elements of a course – content, assessment, and pedagogy.

2.3 Content Assessment and Pedagogy (CAP)

CAP is a course design framework which is adapted from the Backward Design process and is a useful guide to help instructors make student-centric design decisions during the development of courses [10]. At the core of the CAP philosophy is the need to constructively align all the three elements of the course – content, assessment, and pedagogy [11]. The CAP framework guides instructors to reflect

and make a decision on what content needs to be emphasized and less emphasized depending on the learning outcomes of the course. The framework suggests that assessments, both summative and formative, need to be designed with a goal to evaluate the appropriate learning levels as indicated in the enduring outcomes of the course. Open-ended assessments should be designed through the use of rubrics so that the learners are aware of the instructors expectations. The student-centric nature of the CAP model asserts for the need to think about assessment as a way to give students feedback and improve their learning instead of merely utilizing them for the purpose of grading. The pedagogical activities being designed and implemented should be aligned to the levels of assessments so that appropriate teaching practices are implemented to teach content that require higher cognitive levels of learning. The CAP framework therefore provides instructors with design guidelines to thoughtfully create or redesign courses in a student-centric approach.

3 T-CAP

In this section, we introduce the T-CAP framework which is an extension of the CAP framework and addresses the limitations of the TPACK framework. T-CAP as shown in Figure 1 introduces technology as a fourth element of course design process and elaborates on the alignment required between technology and content, technology and pedagogy, and technology and assessment. The required understanding of the relation between technology and assessment for a course is currently overlooked in the TPACK framework and we aim to highlight it's importance to successfully design technology-enhanced learning environments.

Fig. 1. T-CAP Design Framework for Technology-Enhanced Learning

3.1 Technology and Content

The CAP model recommends instructors to prioritize their course content into three categories created by Wiggins and McTighe: Enduring outcomes, Important-to-know outcomes, and Good-to-be-familiar-with outcomes [11]. This categorization is important as most course content are presented as a list of topics and instructors give equal importance to all of them. However, it is not possible for students to retain all the content after the completion of the course. The instructor should have an understanding of which content they expect students to retain long after the end of the course and categorize that content as Enduring Outcomes. Similarly the course content that would support students understanding or attainment of the enduring outcomes should be included as Important-to-Know. The content which is not crucial to the learning experience and students would benefit from just hearing about it should be categorized as Good-To-Know. This categorization is important as it helps the instructor build an understanding of how to prioritize the course content and manage their instructional time efficiently.

Technology tools allows you have the flexibility to present content through varied representations. For example, content provided to students can be made available in the form of text (book chapters, articles, paper publications), audio (podcast, audionotes), presentation (Powerpoint, Prezi, Piktochart etc), and videos (animated, multimedia etc). It is imperative for the instructor to reflect and decide on how should different content in the course should be represented. Content that is included as Enduring Outcomes should be represented in formats such as presentation and video as the technology being used provide you with the tools to design and generate content for deeper conceptual understanding. Similarly, the instructor should align the choice of technology tools used for content representation with the category of the content. Its important to note that usage of same technology tool to design and present all type of content would not be a student-centric approach as the technology usage will not be aligned to the learning outcomes of the course. The selection of the technology tools should therefore be decided by the type of the content, the appropriate format for representation, and technology tools available to create content in that format.

3.2 Technolgy and Assessment

Assessments are often designed and administered to students to grade them and provide a report. However, CAP emphasizes on need to rethink assessments and see them as tools to provide student feedback. It is important for the instructor to give the learners regular feedback throughout the duration of the course so that they are guided during the learning process to potentially achieve mastery in the graded assessments. Both summative and formative assessments should be designed mainly to evaluate the students learning of the enduring outcomes and important-to-know outcomes. As enduring outcomes are the core of students learning experience in the course,

formative assessments should be targeted to provide students regular feedback on their understanding of the enduring outcomes so as to help the learners to attainment them by the end of the course. The levels of mastery expected from students to successfully complete the course should be communicated to them at the start of the course through the design and dissemination of rubrics, which will be used to grade the open-ended assessments. Rubrics could be used a tool to provide transparency of the instructors expectations from the students to achieve the mastery in the course.

The summative assessments being designed need to be aligned to the learning outcomes of the course and should take into account the taxonomy and learning levels mentioned in the outcome. The learning levels of the outcome would drive the format of assessment and the instructor should therefore identify appropriate technology tools to design, administer, and evaluate the assessments. Most instructors do not use formative assessments as it's a time consuming process to administer, assess, and provide regular feedback to the students. However, there are many innovative assessment tools available for instructors to facilitate formative assessments and provide students with immediate feedback. For example, there are many technology tools that would now allow instructors to administer various types of formative assessments such as discussion questions prior to the start of the classes, poll questions during the class, and quizzes after the completion of the class. The many features available in the current technology tools makes it easier for the instructors to administer, collect, and analyze the data. Instructors could now also use built in data analytic tools made available in learning mangemenet systems to automate the data analysis process and get real time instantaneous feedback on the students learning [12]. The use of technology for assessment could therefore open many opportunities for instructors to facilitate formative assessments and provide students with regular feedback on their learning.

3.3 Technology and Pedagogy

The design decisions for the pedagogies to be implemented in a course should be aligned to the content and assessment of the course. The pedagogy should be able to provide students with enough opportunities to practice needed to achieve expected mastery of the enduring outcomes. The practice opportunities provided should be deliberately distributed through the duration of the course. The multiple opportunities provided to the students to practice would help them to store the content in the long term memory and as a result retain it for many years. The mode of the pedagogies implemented should be aligned to the learning levels of the enduring outcomes. Chi's Interactive-Constructive-Active-Passive (ICAP) framework categorizes various pedagogies based on the students' expected actions, engagement, and outcomes during the activities [13]. With regard to the impact, interactive activities are expected to be most effective, followed by constructive, active, and passive.

Instructors who use a range of pedagogical activities need to identify the appropriate technology tools that support their implementation. Attention should be given during the selection of a technology tool to ensure students will have the opportunities to perform all the actions as required by the type of ICAP pedagogy. For example, instructors implementing cooperative learning (an interactive pedagogy) should use technology tools which allow students to enter into breakout rooms and collaborate with each other to perform the given task [14]. Students could be made active during the classroom by asking them to reply to the instructors' questions in the chat box or by responding to poll questions. The usage of technology for instruction also provides flexibility to the instructor to make use of a combination of both synchronous and asynchronous modes of learning. Course content which is good-to-know and sometimes important-to-know can be taught by providing asynchronous learning resources to students. We encourage instructors to reflect on various aspects of the course pedagogies and select a learning management system that supports all their requirements.

4 DISCUSSION AND SUMMARY

We presented the T-CAP model in this study as a design framework to guide instructors looking to adopt technology tools and create technology-enhanced learning environments. The T-CAP model is an extension of the well recognized CAP model that encourages instructors to become designers during the process of developing the course. T-CAP emphasizes on the need to reflect and constructively align technology to the three important elements of the course – content, assessment, and pedagogy. We guide instructors with a range of questions that would prompt them to reflect and understand the alignment between the four elements. Students are considered to be at the core of the T-CAP model and it's important to also consider students' acceptance of the technology tools being utilized in the course. Instructors should evaluate students' digital literacy level and the availability of necessary ICT resources to access the technology tools being integrated into the course. The usage of technology for instructional purpose will be the forefront of conversations during and post the COVID19 pandemic and the instructors should put significant efforts to ensure the technology tools would be aligned to the content, assessment, and pedagogy of the course. Instructors who fail to not align the technology tools being used would create technology-enhanced learning environments which are not student-centric. This could run the risk of overburdening the students with improper technology usage instead of supporting them to achieve the learning outcomes of the course.

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